

A STUDY ON THE MULTIPLE-EXPOSURE NANOSPHERE-LITHOGRAPHY FOR UNIQUE PHOTONIC CRYSTAL

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1 Introduction

Photonic crystals (PCs) are periodic dielectric material arrays characterized by photonic bandgaps (PBGs) or electromagnetic stop bands, which have a functional similarity to the electronic energy gap of semiconductor crystals. The PCs are very receptive to the incorporation of the defect state in the PBGs, which need for applications of the PC to various functional devices such as selective transmission filters, optical waveguides, and microcavities, etc. In a previous paper, we proposed that the omni-PBG of 1D PC can be enlarged by including multiple-periodic structures, and demonstrated theoretically and experimentally that the normalized frequency range for omni-PBG in double-periodic PC can be enhanced approximately twofold than that in single PC.

The characteristics of PBG in 2D PC strongly depend on its primitive lattice structure. Many researches for the PBG engineering have focused on the PC array with square or triangle-type lattice that is the representative primitive cell structure capable of being relatively easily realized. If the 2D PC with complex lattices instead of simple triangle lattice can be designed and realized, it might be a worthy research in the fields of PBG engineering and its application. The aim of the present work is to realize the multi-paired PC arrays with complex lattices using the multiple-exposure nanosphere lithography (MENSL) method. Although the proposed multi-paired PCs are based on the triangle lattice, its one lattice point consists of twin, triple, or quadruple points.

In a previous paper, we reported that the dot- and antidote-type 2D PC arrays of a large area can be fabricated by a double holographic lithography (DHL) and in particular, their primitive lattice structures can be controlled from triangle to square via the change of the rotation angle of the double beams.

2 Experimental

The *p*-type Si (100) wafer was used as a substrate after cleaned by acetone, trichloroethylene, isopropyl alcohol, and DI-water. Then, a diluted polymer resist (PR) DMI-150 with propylene glycol monomethyl ether acetate (PGMEA) was spin-coated on the prepared substrate and prebaked at 80 °C for 60 s. The fabricated nanosphere was self-assembled on the PR-coated Si substrate by a stepped spin coating method.

The MENSL method that is the modified nanosphere lithography (NSL) utilizes a self-assembled nanosphere as a lens mask and an expanded laser as multiple-exposure source. A scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of the self-assembled nanosphere coated on the PR substrate is shown in Fig. 1(a), where a clear monolayer of nanospheres with a triangle lattice was formed.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. (a) SEM images of the self-assembled nanosphere by spin-coating on the polymer resist (b) schematic diagram of the rotation and tilt multiple-exposure system using the He-Cd laser; M, mirror; S, shutter; ND, neutral density filter; OL, objective lens; P, pinhole; and CL, collimating lens.

The patterning was optically exposed onto Fig. 1(a) sample by using an expanded laser exposure setup. A single laser beam (He-Cd laser, 442 nm, $h\nu = 2.80$ eV) was utilized as a light source for the exposure system. The beam was routed by two dielectric mirrors and expanded to a diameter of ~ 100 mm using a beam expander consisting of objective lens (numerical aperture of 0.65), a pinhole (diameter of $10 \mu\text{m}$), and collimating lens, as detailed in Fig. 1(b). The He-Cd laser at 442 nm and 120 mW was expanded to 70 mm of beam diameter with a power density ranges of 1.5 – 2.0 mW. The sample holder and rotation stage consisted of a practicable rotation and tilt, allowing the incident angle (θ , γ) to be easily changed and precisely controlled.

3 Result and Discussion

Figure 2(a) shows SEM images of 2D PC patterns arrays fabricated in the PR via the process of the single-exposure NSL and development, where the exposure time for 5 sec. The 2D PCs by the NSL with different filling factors can be fabricated by controlling the exposure time, e.e., increase of exposure time leads to expanding the size of patterned dot. As shown in Fig. 2(b) and (c), the unique PCs was fabricated by quadruple and multiple exposure at rotation and tilting.

Fig. 2. SEM images of (a) 2D PC patterns formed by the single-exposure nanosphere lithography; patterned PR top and side view, the fabricated unique PCs patterns by the (b) quadruple exposure, (c) multiple exposure.

In particular, the NSL method was fabricated as hexagonal type 2D PCs, but the MENSLS method was able to fabricate variable shape periodic array (i.e., pair-PCs, PQC, character-PCs, etc.). In addition, the period size by the NSL method was equal to nanosphere size, but the period size by the MENSLS method was able to be fabricated smaller than the nanosphere size at the control of θ and γ angle.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. Schematic geometric setup (a) and calculation flowchart (b) of the calculation process of Brillouin zone spectrum of photonic lattice.

Figure 3 represents the calculation process of the BZ spectra, where Figure 3 (a) and (b) are the schematic geometric setup and calculation flowchart, respectively. A coherent input beam is launched into the photonic crystals, then the fast Fourier transform (FFT) is utilized to obtain the output spectrum. In addition, a medial filter is applied to make the spectrum more distinguishable.

Figure 4 show the photonic band structures of unique 2D photonic crystals, (a) and (b) are calculated photonic band structures for single dot and quadruple dot with triangle lattice base, respectively. The change of photonic band gaps be

caused by transition of Brillouin zone (BZ). The evolution of the slowly varying amplitude of the light wave in photonic crystal is governed by the normalized paraxial Schrodinger equation

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \psi + \frac{1}{2} \nabla_{\perp}^2 \psi + V(x,y) \psi = 0$$

Where ψ is the complex amplitude of the light wave, $\nabla_{\perp}^2 = \partial_x^2 + \partial_y^2$, $V(x,y)$ is the refractive index potential of the photonic lattice. Here I use optically induced photonic lattice in a 2D photonic crystals as an example. Then $V(x,y)$ is generated with the saturation nonlinearity, reading $V(x,y) = E_0 I_l / (1 + I_l)$, where E_0 is the applied field, and I_l is the normalized intensity of the lattice beam (used for inducing the lattice structure).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. The photonic band structures of unique photonic crystals. (a) single dot; (d) quadruple paired dot.

4 Conclusion

This study has demonstrated the novel method for variable shape PCs fabrication using the multiple-exposure system and nanosphere. The 2D PC arrays exhibited various shapes of the periodic lattice structures from original (triangle, square) to paired arrays according to the change of the rotation and tilt angle for multiple-exposure. The study result suggest that the MENSL method is a promising tool to fabricate various 2D PCs (multiple-pair, character, more fined) with the periodic array of a large area. Further studies to design and calculate fabrication of 2D PC patterns are presently in progress.

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